

Humin Fraction of Soil Humus

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SOIL organic matter and, in particular, the soil humus is no doubt one of the most complex materials existing in nature. The term "Soil Humus" is used to refer more specifically to the non-living components of heterogeneous nature resulting from microbial and chemical transformation of organic debris. As a component of soils, the organic matter is the resultant of a number of complex processes characteristic of the environment in which it is found. Residues of vegetative cover and leaf falls might be termed the parent materials from which it is formed. Its synthesis and degradation constitute a dynamic process and depend largely on the soil environment.

As a component of soil, organic matter can be divided into two major groups :

(1) Non-humic substances-unaltered remains of plant and animal tissues and also organic compounds that have definite characteristics.

(2) Humic substances-transformed products bearing little or no resemblance to the anatomical structure from which they are derived.

Depending on solubility the humic substances can be subdivided into (i) fulvic acid, soluble both in acid and alkali, (ii) humic acid, soluble in alkali and insoluble in acid and (iii) humin, not easily soluble in acid and alkali.

The chemistry of humic and fulvic acids has been extensively reviewed by Hayes and Swift¹ recently and a vast amount of literature is available on the characterisation of humic and fulvic acids. Here we shall discuss only about the nature and characteristics of the humin fraction of soil humus.

Humin is commonly believed to be that fraction which is strongly bound to the clay after the usual alkali extraction of humus acids and is known to resist extraction. Tyurin and Gutkina² during their studies with the chernozem soils showed that a part of the humic substances present in the form of humin fraction, dissolved in alkali after removing the humic acid of the decalcified soil by means of 0.1 N NaOH, subjecting the soil residues to short acidification with 5N HNO₃ and then treating with HF to break the stable linkage with silicate minerals and still further treating with acetyl bromide to remove the unhumified fraction. They concluded that

the humin fraction represents a complex of substances similar to that isolated from the decalcified soil by alkali solution ; it consists of nothing but humic and fulvic acids. The humic acids from the humin fraction contain a somewhat lower percentage of oxygen and hydrogen than the humic acids extracted from the decalcified soil. Similar results were obtained by Khan³ during investigations on the humins of podsol soil. Zyrin⁴ also studied the humins of podsol and chernozem soils and came to the same conclusion.

It has, however, been found that the humin fraction is also amenable to alkali extraction but the amount extracted is very small. If the treatment with alkali is repeated, nearly 50-60% of the humin fraction can be recovered⁵. What is more interesting is that this fraction can be subfractionated into fulvic, hmatomelanic and humic acids⁶. This would, therefore, suggest that humin is nothing but a composite mixture just like the bulk of the extract obtained by a single treatment. Table 1 shows the percentages of carbon in different extractions extracted by 0.5N sodium carbonate solution from two soils of India (Brown forest soil of Dehra Dun and Deep gray forest soil of Assam). It was found that the carbon content in humus gradually decreased with the successive extractions and 35-36% were extracted after 13 extractions⁵.

TABLE-1. PERCENTAGES OF CARBON IN DIFFERENT EXTRACTIONS EXTRACTED BY 0.5 N Na₂CO₃ SOLUTION

No. of extractions	Dehra Dun Soil	Assam Soil
1st Extraction	0.488	0.368
2nd "	0.390	0.290
3rd "	0.225	0.158
4th "	0.135	0.095
5th "	0.095	0.055
6th "	0.058	0.039
7th "	0.042	0.028
8th "	0.035	0.023
9th "	0.028	0.019
10th "	0.022	0.019
11th "	0.019	0.010
12th "	0.012	0.006
13th "	0.008	0.002
Total	1.557	1.107
Percentage of carbon in soil residues	2.994	2.368

The results clearly indicate that the binding capacity of the humus with clay gradually increases

and there is the progressive difficulty in extracting the humus with alkali solution.

Although the structure of humic or fulvic acid is not yet known, it is possible to say something about the functional groups they contain. Humic acids comprise both colloidal and true acids containing functional groups such as carboxyl, hydroxyl (both phenolic and alcoholic), free amino and imino groups^{7,8}. The acidic nature of humic acid was established by conductometric titration with a weak base⁹. Estimates of basicity were attempted by the application of the Ostwald rule, which relates to equi-valent conductivity at two different dilutions to the number of stages of neutralisation.

The sum total of the acid groups is determined with alkali or barium hydroxide titration usually of solution or suspension, and the content of carboxyl groups, by reaction with Ca-acetate; the difference between these values equals the contents of phenolic hydroxyl groups^{7,8}.

Tyurin and Gutkina² in their studies on humic acids obtained from humin fractions of humus of chernozem soils observed that they had a lower absorption capacity. They showed that the meq. of calcium per 100g of substance obtained by treatment with 5N HNO₃ was 365.5 and that obtained by treatment with 5N H₂SO₄ was 379.2, whereas that of the humic acid from decalcified soil was 459.3 meq/100g. They concluded that humic acids from humin are of simpler nature than those extracted from soil after decalcification.

Banerjee and Mukherjee^{10,11} after studying the electrochemical properties of the humic and fulvic acids of the successive extracts obtained from the humin fractions of Assam and Dehra Dun soils with 0.5 N Na₂CO₃ solution observed that the total acidity of the successive extracts of humic acids decreased but the reverse was the case for fulvic acids (Table-2). They suggested that humic acids having relatively lower acidity, i.e., containing a smaller number of acid functions, are involved in forming stronger clay-humus complex but in case of fulvic acids those having relatively higher total acidities are not so involved. As a result, humic substances of these fractions could be extracted only by means of repeated treatments. This was verified by the fact that by treating Ca-clay with humic and fulvic acids in the Na-form of the different extractions, humic acids of lower acidity were fixed strongly, whereas those of higher acidity were not, and by treating the Ca-Na-humate complex with 0.5N Na₂CO₃ solution, the humic acids of higher acidity could be extracted in greater amount; the amounts are gradually in decreasing order with the decrease of the total acidities but in the case of fulvic acids those having higher acidity were fixed strongly⁶ (Table-3).

TABLE—2. C.E.C. IN ME/100G. OF HUMIC AND FULVIC ACIDS OF DIFFERENT EXTRACTS

Substance	c.e.c. in me/1000g		c.e.c. in me/100g	
	conductometric methods	potentiometric method	conductometric method	potentiometric method
	Humic acids from Assam soil		Fulvic acids from Assam soil	
1st Extraction	650	640	850	660
2nd "	607	580	865	600
3rd "	532	525	895	735
4th "	465	475	1690	1500
5th "	467	445	1780	1570
6th "	426	394	1510	1250
	Humic acids from Dehra Dun Soil		Fulvic acids from Dehra Dun Soil	
1st Extraction	690	675	594	415
2nd "	610	598	660	465
3rd "	520	490	660	465
4th "	468	450	830	803
5th "	430	415	875	846

TABLE—3. SORPTION AND DESORPTION OF Na-HUMATE AND Na-FULVATE BY Ca-CLAY

Sample	Per cent added	Per cent unadsorbed	Per cent adsorbed	Per cent released after one extraction	Per cent fixed
	Na-Humate				
1st Extraction	1.76	0.69	1.07	1.07	0.004
2nd "	1.76	0.57	1.19	0.88	0.31
3rd "	1.76	0.20	1.56	0.57	0.99
4th "	1.76	0.10	1.67	0.54	1.12
5th "	1.76	0.04	1.71	0.47	1.24
6th "	1.76	—	1.76	0.37	1.39
	Na-Fulvate				
1st Extrac-tion	6.30	4.41	1.89	1.57	0.32
2nd "	5.77	3.78	1.99	1.26	0.73
3rd "	5.50	3.62	1.88	1.26	0.62
4th "	5.25	3.15	2.10	1.05	1.05
5th "	4.20	3.05	2.15	0.73	1.42
6th "	3.57	0.63	2.94	0.63	2.31

From the above results, it is logical to suppose that the humic acids of the humin fraction are of simpler nature and low molecular weight compounds. But, since humic or fulvic acids are heterogeneous mixture of substances varying in charge densities, molecular weight and total acidity, the smaller the molecule, the higher is the total acidity¹²⁻¹⁵ and the smallest molecules interact strongest with the mineral part of the soil^{16,17}. Moreover, from the viscosity measurement with the different extracts, Banerjee and Gupta¹⁸ showed that the intrinsic viscosity of the successively extracted humic acid gradually increased. This indicates greater polymerisation of the successively extracted humic acids. Viscosity average molecular weights also increased with successively extracted humic acids (Table-4).

TABLE-4. INTRINSIC VISCOSITIES AND MOLECULAR WEIGHTS OF THE EXTRACTS

Sample	$[\eta]_{\text{salt free}}$ (from Fuoss and Strauss plot) ml/g			$[\eta]_{0.1M \text{ NaCl}}$ ml/g			Viscosity average molecular weight $\times 10^{-4}$ (Raneg)
	Dehra Dun Soil	Assam Soil	Dehra Dun Soil	Assam Soil	Dehra Dun Soil	Assam Soil	
	1st Ext.	16.7	17.1	4.3	4.7	3.95-5.25	
2nd "	16.9	18.3	4.3	4.7	4.04-5.43	4.46-6.35	
3rd "	17.9	20.6	4.3	4.7	4.32-5.89	5.13-8.03	
4th "	19.2	21.3	4.3	4.7	4.72-6.97	5.37-8.58	
5th "	—	22.0	—	4.7	—	5.58-9.13	
6th "	—	22.5	—	4.7	—	5.75-9.55	

From these observations it may be concluded that the flexibility, molecular weight and also the chain length increase with the successively extracted humic acids. This was further verified from the determination of coagulation threshold values⁶. The amounts of calcium chloride for the beginning of coagulation and for complete coagulation were different and gradually increased with the successively extracted humic acids. Humic acid molecules are in general composed of an aromatic part and an aliphatic part. Of these two, the aromatic part is likely to be hydrophobic in aqueous medium and hence susceptible to coagulation by electrolytes. The aliphatic part is, on the other hand, likely to be hydrophilic and hence will resist coagulation in aqueous medium. In this context, the successive extracts, which are more and more resistant to coagulation, may be assumed to consist of a larger proportion of the aliphatic part. An alternative possibility is that the degree of polymerisation of humic acids in the successive extracts increases as is shown by the progressive difficulty in extraction of the humic acids as well as their sorption and desorption characteristics. Therefore, the humin fraction is represented mainly by humic acids of high molecular weight and of more complex materials than the humic acid extracted by a single treatment with alkali from the decalcified soil. Their loss of the capacity for dissolving in alkali is due to the firmness of linkage with the clay minerals present in the soil.

The dominant factors determining the nature of clay-organic interactions are the properties of the organic compound the water content of the system, the nature of the exchangeable cations on the clay surface and the properties of the particular clay mineral¹⁹. The size and shape of the cation also play an important role²⁰. Aleksandrova²¹ and also Greenland^{22,23} suggested that stable clay-humus complexes are formed with the help of sesquioxides which make specific bridges between the functional groups of humic substance and crystalline lattice of clay minerals. The clay surface can also adsorb organic compounds through hydrogen bonding between its oxygen and hydroxyls and acidic functional groups of humic materials²⁴. The formation of hydrogen bonds has also been found to occur

between a polar organic molecule and a hydrated exchangeable cation through the bridge of hydration water²⁵, or between two organic cation species²⁶.

The linkage will be more stable where there is an interaction between humate and minerals of the montmorillonite type when the adsorption of humate takes place in the mineral lattice²⁷⁻²⁹. In case of kaolinite, humic acid molecules are adsorbed on the surface of the crystal and the -OH and COOH groups in the humic acid take part in the linkage⁷; it may be inferred that there is a possibility of formation of "water bridge"-like compounds¹⁹ linking polymeric humic acid molecules with the exchangeable metal cations of the clay surface. The interaction is dependent on the degrees of saturation of the metal ions and also on the nature of cations present in the clay. The binding is more strong in presence of iron and less in presence of calcium. Aluminium has an intermediate effect³⁰. Greenland²² feels that hydrous oxides of iron and aluminium are the most important materials involved in interaction between clays and organic compounds. Again, the humic substances interact with expanding clays by adsorbing on external surfaces and in interlamellar spaces³¹. The latter reaction is specially important in the case of fulvic acid^{32,33}. But evidence has also been presented questioning the possibility of penetration of humus substances into the interlamellar spaces of clay^{22,23,34}. Unless we know the actual chemical structure of humic acid molecule, it is very difficult to interpret the experimental data with certainty.

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